

Viscosity and Molecular Interaction in Binary Mixtures of Some Polar and Nonpolar Liquids with Dimethylsulphoxide

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Manuscript received 29 November 1977, revised 6 February 1978, accepted 23 March 1978

Viscosities of some polar and non-polar liquids in admixture with DMSO have been measured at 30° and 40° and the results have been examined in the light of the relations developed for binary mixtures. The value of the interaction energy 'W' is calculated for each of the mixture at 30°.

VISCOSITY data of binary liquid mixtures have been employed to yield information regarding the nature of interaction^{1,2} in solution. In continuation with our work on molecular interaction in liquid mixture, it was considered desirable to undertake viscosity measurements of binary liquid mixtures of some non-polar liquids, e.g., Benzene, Dioxane, Toluene, and polar like Chlorobenzenes and Nitrobenzene liquids with DMSO. Literature reveals that very little attention seems to have been paid³⁻⁵ to determine the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures containing DMSO as one of the components. Our excess volume of mixing⁶ measurement have shown dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions between the components. The results of viscosity measurements have been analysed on the basis of the relations developed by Katti and Chaudhari⁷ and adopted by Raman, Naidu and Krishnan⁸, for non-ideal solutions.

Materials and Methods

DMSO and other liquids were purified and purity was checked as reported earlier.⁶

Viscosity of mixtures was determined with a modified Ubbelohde viscometer having appropriate auxiliary equipment to keep off atmospheric moisture from the system as far as possible. The accuracy of the viscometer was checked by measuring viscosities of pure Benzene and Chlorobenzene. The agreement with the corresponding literature values appears to be quite good.

Mixtures of known compositions were prepared by weight, precaution being taken to keep the solvent and solution out of contact with atmosphere as far as possible. The mixture was transferred to the viscometer which was then suspended in a water thermostat controlled to $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The time of flow of the liquid through capillary was noted. Density of the mixture was also determined side by side with a caped dilatometer. For each system measurements were made at 30° and 40° and the viscosity was then obtained from density and time of flow data in the usual manner.

Results and Discussion

The viscosity of mixtures (η_B) was found to decrease with the increase in temperature. Except the DMSO+Nitrobenzene system, all mixtures deviate negatively from the mixture law, i.e., the viscosity of the mixture is less than expected from mixture law. For DMSO+Nitrobenzene system, η_B -values show almost an ideal behaviour at 30° and 40°.

In order to substantiate the above finding, the data were examined in the light of conclusions drawn by Fort and Moore⁹, by calculating excess viscosity of mixing, η^E represented by

$$\eta^E = \eta_B - (\eta_A X_A + \eta_B X_B)$$

where η_B is the viscosity of the mixture, η_A, η_B are the viscosities and X_A, X_B are the mole fractions of components A and B respectively. The values of η^E so obtained for different systems are given in Table 1.

In another approach to describe the viscosity of binary mixtures, Grunberg and Nissan⁹ suggested

$$\ln \eta_{mix} = X_A \ln \eta_A + X_B \ln \eta_B + X_A X_B d$$

where d is proportional to W/RT and W being the interchange energy. The parameter has the same significance as given by Guggenheim¹⁰ in the treatment of his regular solution theory and d has been regarded as a better measure of the strength of interaction between the components in solution. The values of d obtained are also given in Table 1.

It may be noted from Table 1 that except for DMSO+nitrobenzene, all mixtures have negative values of η^E over the entire concentration range. In DMSO+Nitrobenzene system, there is no measurable viscosity change of mixing showing that the system behaves ideally.

TABLE-1 EXCESS VISCOSITY (η^E) AND FACTOR 'd' OF MIXTURES OF DMSO(B) WITH DIFFERENT LIQUIDS (A)

Mole fraction X_A	30°		40°	
	η^E	d	η^E	d
DMSO(B) + Benzene (A)				
0.2	-0.161	-0.172	-0.110	-0.057
0.3	-0.207	-0.207	-0.147	-0.087
0.4	-0.218	-0.230	-0.182	-0.191
0.5	-0.232	-0.350	-0.165	-0.110
0.6	-0.217	-0.278	-0.149	-0.105
0.7	-0.175	-0.263	-0.124	-0.098
0.8	-0.128	-0.273	-0.089	-0.100
DMSO(B) + Toluene (A)				
0.2	-0.073	+0.273	-0.105	+0.001
0.3	-0.077	+0.350	-0.115	+0.093
0.4	-0.093	+0.345	-0.112	+0.162
0.5	-0.088	+0.469	-0.099	+0.235
0.6	-0.071	+0.477	-0.095	+0.229
0.7	-0.055	+0.537	-0.042	+0.505
0.8	-0.039	+0.604	-0.019	+0.639
DMSO(B) + Chlorobenzene (A)				
0.2	-0.105	-0.092	-0.074	-0.066
0.3	-0.138	-0.116	-0.099	-0.034
0.4	-0.154	-0.126	-0.113	-0.099
0.5	-0.172	-0.193	-0.118	-0.118
0.6	-0.138	-0.237	-0.122	-0.188
0.7	-0.151	-0.291	-0.107	-0.218
0.8	-0.127	-0.433	-0.035	-0.318
DMSO(B) + Nitrobenzene (A)				
0.2	+0.002	+0.001	-0.001	-0.011
0.3	+0.002	-0.004	0.000	-0.009
0.4	+0.004	-0.002	-0.001	-0.004
0.5	0.000	-0.005	-0.008	-0.007
0.6	+0.004	+0.002	0.000	-0.001
0.7	+0.003	+0.004	0.000	-0.023
0.8	+0.002	-0.006	-0.001	-0.053
DMSO(B) + Dioxane (A)				
0.2	-0.111	-0.332	-0.099	-0.345
0.3	-0.149	-0.364	-0.096	-0.234
0.4	-0.162	-0.364	-0.100	-0.214
0.5	-0.169	-0.384	-0.116	-0.271
0.6	-0.151	-0.366	-0.111	-0.291
0.7	-0.132	-0.390	-0.090	-0.276
0.8	-0.103	-0.422	-0.068	-0.332

The data of d shows that for DMSO+Benzene, DMSO+Chlorobenzene and DMSO+Dioxane, the d-values are negative at both the temperatures over the entire concentration range; d-values generally become less negative with rise in temperature. For DMSO+Toluene, the values of d are positive. The negative values of d and η^E in the mixtures of DMSO with Benzene, Dioxane and Chlorobenzene shows a somewhat weaker interaction. Nigam and Mahl¹¹ discussed the sign of η^E and d in terms of complex formation between the components. It would be unreasonable to expect complexing in our systems. Perhaps, difference in the size of molecules may also be important in deciding the sign of η^E and d.

Another approach to study molecular interaction in binary liquid mixtures with the help of viscosity data is that of Katti and Chaudhary⁷ and Raman et

al⁸ using Eyring concept of viscosity, they obtained the expression, viz.

$$\ln \eta_s V_s = X_A \ln \eta_A V_A + X_B \ln \eta_B V_B + X_A X_B \frac{W}{RT}$$

where W is the energy of viscous flow. This approach, perhaps would give a more direct idea about the type and extent of interaction between the components. The values of W at 0.5 mole fraction concentration, are given in Table 2.

TABLE-2 VALUES OF 'W' AT EQUIMOLAR CONCENTRATION AT 30°

System	W in cal./mole
DMSO+Benzene	-245.8
DMSO+Toluene	+234.6
DMSO+Chlorobenzene	+39.1
DMSO+Nitrobenzene	+368.6
DMSO+Dioxane	-279.4

Large negative values of W in DMSO+Benzene and DMSO+Dioxane systems show an appreciable dipole-induced dipole interaction between the components. Appreciable interaction in these systems is also shown by negative values of excess volume of mixing⁶. Positive values of W in DMSO+Toluene, DMSO+Chlorobenzene and DMSO+Nitrobenzene shows weak dipole-dipole interaction between the components as supported by our positive values of V_m^E in these systems⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. S. Tewari, Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing laboratory facilities. One of us (S.A.) is obliged to C.S.I.R., for the financial help.

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